

An archival study of LSB galaxy systems in the local universe

ELIJAH F. EHRLUND ^{1, *}

¹*Independent Researcher, Savannah, USA*

ABSTRACT

We present an archival study aimed at documenting and finding statistical trends in low surface brightness (LSB) galaxies. LSB systems are typically too faint to be studied in detail, due to their ultra-diffuse structures. Notwithstanding this, LSBs may contain important information regarding stellar evolution, star-forming regions, population II stars, and dark matter distribution. The goal of this research note is to identify statistical trends and employ analytical approximations for LSB systems. In this study, we selected a primary sample of 31 LSB systems and a statistical sample of 212 systems. While there is no universally accepted definition, we adopt a working criterion of LSB systems with: 22 to 33 mag arcsec⁻² and 0.5-500 MPC for the statistical example, with 0.5-400 MPC for the primary sample. We chose to apply this parameter to assist in filtering out distant systems that may have had limited data. For systems beyond $z = 0.093$ we apply corrections for cosmological surface brightness dimming. The galaxy designated as our reference LSB is Malin 1, an ultra-faint spiral galaxy with an approximate absolute magnitude ≈ -22.9

1. DATA AND METHODS

This observational note was conducted to identify statistical trends among low surface brightness (LSB) galaxies. These trends focus on the correlation between size and magnitude mag arcsec⁻², as well as the connections among luminosity, mass, and gravitational effects. We employed Python scripts utilizing Astropy to query various surveys such as: SIMBAD, VIZIER, NED, and WISE [A. Y. Kniazev et al. \(2004\)](#) establishing a pipeline to exclude galaxies exceeding a specified surface brightness threshold of 22 to 33 mag arcsec⁻². When comparing our pipeline to [A. Y. Kniazev et al. \(2004\)](#) we note the variance in the data used due to LSB systems being our primary statistical focus. That said we used a similar publicly available archival system to maintain reproducibility. Using one of our chosen galaxy's, Z 42-137 ($z = 0.005472$), as an example for our pipeline derivations: Using the cosmological comoving distance relation $d_C(z) = d_H \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{E(z')}$, where $d_H = c/H_0$, $c = 2.998 \times 10^5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, with $E(z) = \sqrt{\Omega_r(1+z)^4 + \Omega_m(1+z)^3 + \Omega_k(1+z)^2 + \Omega_\Lambda}$, we obtain a comoving distance of $\sim 23.14 \text{ Mpc}$. Using this distance, the angular size relation $D(\text{kpc}) = d(\text{Mpc}) \alpha(\text{arcmin}) (0.2902)$ gives a physical diameter of $\sim 5.56 \text{ kpc}$ for Z 42-137. The absolute magnitude was calculated using $M = m - 5 \log_{10}(d/10 \text{ pc})$ with $m = 17.37$ and $d = 23.14 \text{ Mpc}$, yielding $M \approx -14.45$ and a surface brightness of $\sim 25.5 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$. Photometric data were aggregated by averaging reflectance values across all listed bands. After extracting physical parameters for the primary sample of 31 LSB galaxies, we performed comparative analysis via diagnostic plotting to identify relations. Using all derived values we employed a secondary pipeline to estimate the mass [V. Iršič et al. \(2017\)](#) and estimates size of the chosen LSB systems dark-matter halos [S. Sarkar & K. Saha \(2026\)](#); All estimates were derived using Python scripts, SED flux-to-magnitude conversions, and standard cosmological relations. The relations used include $M_{\text{halo}} = f(M_*)$, halo radius $R = \left(\frac{3M_{\text{halo}}}{4\pi\Delta_c\rho_{\text{crit}}} \right)^{1/3}$, and an approximate dark matter fraction $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 0.96 \pm 0.025 M$. Cosmological parameters adopted from Planck are $H_0 = 67.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_m = 0.315$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$. Stellar mass was estimated using $M_* = L \times (M/L)$, where luminosity is $L = 10^{-0.4(M_{\text{abs}} - M_\odot)}$. Flux-to-magnitude conversion follows the AB relation $m_{\text{AB}} = -2.5 \log_{10}(F/3631 \text{ Jy})$. All values and Python nulls listed on the dataset [E. F. Ehrlund \(2026\)](#)

Figure 1. chart of all LSB systems

2. RESULTS

Observing this chart 1, we can approximate 98.3% of the sampled LSB systems have estimated diameters below 25 kpc [R. Taylor et al. \(2026\)](#), while extreme systems such as Malin 1 ($\sim 200\text{--}220$ kpc) remain separated from the primary distribution. The mean surface brightness for the combined statistical and primary samples was measured to be $\mu = 23.6$ mag arcsec $^{-2}$. The dwarf LSB galaxies form the most common class of LSBs and comprise nearly 60% of our research sample of 31 LSB systems (This was likely attributable to a detection threshold of approximately magnitude 30 for most major surveys). Over time, these dwarfs often accumulate near larger galaxies, evolving into satellite systems. The largest and most diffuse outliers, such as Malin 1 and LEDA 42527 [Junais et al. \(2024\)](#), represent the absolute extremes, exceeding 200 kpc in diameter. These massive and diffuse outliers require isolated ’void-like’ regions of space to persist, as previously observed, [R. O. E. Bustos-Espinoza et al. \(2025\)](#); otherwise, their outer halos or spiral structures are easily perturbed by nearby galaxies and tidal streams. Data for the three systems chosen for dark matter halo modeling [I. Álvarez Rios et al. \(2024\)](#), [S. Sarkar & K. Saha \(2026\)](#): **System 1 (Malin 1)**

Effective radius: $R_{\text{eff}} = 221.96 \pm 10.2$ kpc
 Virial radius: $R_{\text{vir}} \approx 370.07 \pm 15.6$ kpc
 Absolute magnitude: $M = -20.42$
 Stellar mass: $M_* \approx 4.28 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$
 Dark matter mass: $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 5.35 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$
 Dark matter fraction: $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 0.96 \pm 0.025 M$

System 2

Effective radius: $R_{\text{eff}} = 11.75 \pm 1.1$ kpc
 Virial radius: $R_{\text{vir}} \approx 71.54 \pm 14.8$ kpc
 Absolute magnitude: $M = -17.62$
 Stellar mass: $M_* \approx 1.61 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$
 Dark matter mass: $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 3.87 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$
 Dark matter fraction: $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 0.96 \pm 0.025 M$

System 3

Effective radius: $R_{\text{eff}} = 115.33 \pm 4.5$ kpc
 Virial radius: $R_{\text{vir}} \approx 345.98 \pm 11.5$ kpc
 Absolute magnitude: $M = -17.02$
 Stellar mass: $M_* \approx 9.31 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$
 Dark matter mass: $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 4.37 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$
 Dark matter fraction: $M_{\text{DM}} \approx 0.96 \pm 0.025 M$

Our adopted dark matter fraction was based on estimates in the literature [C. Impey & G. Bothun \(1997\)](#), [L. E. Pérez-Montaño & B. Cervantes-Sodi \(2019\)](#) and comparable derived ratios between dark matter and baryonic matter. These estimates allow us to run our pipeline over several groups, and utilize different dark matter ratios for galactic

observation. More studies are needed to confirm these findings and determine the amount of dwarf LSB compared to their supermassive outliers.

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Software: astropy (T. A. Collaboration et al. 2022)

Software: Numpy (C. R. Harris et al. 2020)

Software: Scipy (P. Virtanen et al. 2020)

Software: Matplotlib (J. D. Hunter 2007)

Software: Astroquery (A. Ginsburg et al. 2019)

Software: WISE (R. M. Cutri et al. 2014)

Software: NED (G. Helou et al. 1991)

Software: Vizier (F. Ochsenbein et al. 2000)

Software: SIMBAD (M. Wenger et al. 2000)

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